

Bohemian Morals in W. S. Maugham's Novel "Theatre"

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Abstract: As is known, a stylistic device is a conscious and intentional strengthening of some typical structural and a semantic property of a linguistic unit (neutral or expressive), elevated to a generalized status and thus becoming a generative model. A stylistic device is an abstract sample, a form into which any content can be poured.

Keywords: creative linguistic personality, cognitive metaphor, thinking and consciousness, translation.

Cognitive linguistics is the foundation for new emphases in understanding language. These emphases provide certain opportunities for studying the interaction between human consciousness and cognitive processes. Cognitive linguistics is a separate direction of linguistics, which is characterized by language as a general cognitive mechanism and a cognitive tool located at the center of science. The central problem of cognitive linguistics is the construction of a model of language communication as a basis for knowledge exchange.

The word is the main means of access to conceptual knowledge. Thanks to this access, we have the opportunity to add other conceptual features to intellectual activity, even if these features are not named by the given word. Linguistic nomination is the key means of using the concept in intellectual activity. The word introduces the concept into our awareness, makes it active and causes the process of thinking. Words can be classified according to different principles: morphological (parts of speech), semantic (synonyms, antonyms, thematic), stylistic and other types of classification. In each of these classifications, lexical and/or grammatical meaning takes on different manifestations. In morphological classification, words are grouped according to their grammatical meanings, in semantic classification - according to logical (referential), in stylistic classification - according to stylistic [4,66].

Lexical meanings are closely related to concepts. Sometimes they are identified with concepts. But a concept is a purely logical category, whereas meaning is a linguistic one. In linguistics, it is necessary to consider meaning as a representation of a concept through one of its properties. A concept, as is known, is multifaceted; it is characterized by a number of properties. Meaning takes one of these properties and makes it a representative of the concept as a whole. Thus, meaning in relation to the concept becomes a kind of metonymy. This statement is important because it additionally explains the stylistic function of some meanings. One and the same concept can be presented in several linguistic manifestations (meanings), but, as paradoxical as it may sound, each manifestation causes an insignificant (and sometimes significant) modification of the concept, in other words, it reveals hidden or unknown properties of the concept. The lexical meaning of a word, which can be described as a component of meaning inherent in the word as a linguistic unit, i.e. repeated in all forms of the

word. The difference between lexical and grammatical components of meaning is not to be found in the difference in the concepts underlying these two types of meaning, but rather in the way they are conveyed. For example, the concept of plurality can be expressed by the lexical meaning of the plurality of the world; it can also be expressed by the forms of different words regardless of their lexical meaning, such as boys , girls , joys , etc. The concept of relationship can be expressed by the lexical meaning of a word. In addition, a concept is an idea that combines abstract, concrete-associative and emotional-evaluative features and the history of the concept's creation. A concept is a personal interpretation of an objective meaning and a concept of at least meaning. A concept is also an abstract scientific concept expressed in forms of meaning. Such forms are: image, concept and symbol.

Theatre is a form of performing art. Although any performance can be considered theatre, as a performing art it focuses almost exclusively on live performers creating a self-contained drama. A performance is considered dramatic if it creates the illusion of a performance. By this broad definition, theatre has existed since the dawn of humanity, as a result of the human tendency to tell stories. Since its inception, theatre has taken many forms, using speech, gesture, music, dance, and spectacle, integrating other performing arts, often as well as visual ones, into a single art form. The word comes from the ancient Greek theatre , meaning "place of seeing." We have conducted a study of the concept of the concept and the concept of THEATRE in particular, and now we can consider the concept of THEATRE in the novel by W. S. Maugham "Theatre". The analysis of 20 fragments showed that the concept of THEATRE is widely represented in the novel.

In the following fragment we can see the author's special attitude to the theatre: " That 's because the public is not really interested in the Theatre . In the great days of the English stage people did not go to see plays, they went to see players. It did not matter what Kemble and Mrs. Siddons were doing . People went to see them. And even now, though I do not deny that if a play is bad you "Fail, I claim that if a play is good, the audience goes to see the actors, not the play."

Julia's example shows us what things are important for actors and help them to remain popular: "She made clothes in Paris, both for the stage and for private life, and the dressmakers said that no one brought them more orders. She had a fine figure, everyone admitted it; she was rather tall for a woman, and she had long legs. It was a pity she never had the chance to play Rosalind , she would have looked so good in boyish clothes. Of course, it is too late now, but perhaps it is good that she did not take the risk. Although one would have thought that with her brilliance, her roguery, her sense of comedy, she would have been ideal. The critics did not like her Beatrice very much . It was a damned empty verse. Her voice, her rather low rich voice with an effective huskiness, which squeezed the heart in an emotional passage or gave so much humor to a comedy line, sounded wrong when she uttered it.

The literary character retellings also reflect the concept of the theatre: "In this business you have to take the rough with the smooth. You are the best actress in England" [4;79]. Her heart ached, despite the brilliant performance she had given during the day; and "almost sincerely, with sighs, sad looks and broken phrases, she made him understand that her life was empty, and in spite of the long success of her career she could not help feeling that she had missed something. Sometimes she thought of the villa at Sorrento on the Gulf of Naples" [2;141]. In this case, the real Theatre is represented by the author. The most common definition of a concept is the following: a concept is a discrete mental creation, which is the basic unit of a person's intellectual code. This code is characterized by an internal structure. It is the result of the cognitive activity of a person and society and carries complex and encyclopedic information about an object and phenomenon, as well as a social attitude to this phenomenon. Concepts can be classified by the type of cognition and reflection of reality, since these types underlie the method of identifying and describing a concept.

As is known, a stylistic device is a conscious and intentional strengthening of some typical structural and/or semantic property of a linguistic unit (neutral or expressive), elevated to a generalized status and thus becoming a generative model. A stylistic device is an abstract sample, a form into which any content can be poured. Stylistic devices are a conscious and intentional, literary use of some facts of language (except for expressive means), in which the most essential features (both structural and semantic) of linguistic forms are raised to a generalized level and thereby represent a generative model. A stylistic device is an intentional change in the fixed (usual) distribution of linguistic units in speech. The most common definition of a concept is the following: a concept is a discrete mental creation, which is the basic unit of a person's intellectual code. This code is characterized by an internal structure. It is the result of the cognitive activity of a person and society and carries complex and encyclopedic information about an object and phenomenon, as well as a social attitude towards this phenomenon.

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